

A Case Report On Herlyn-Werner-Wunderlich Syndrome With A Huge Endometrioma

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Abstract

Background: Herlyn-Werner-Wunderlich syndrome (HWWs) is a rare congenital urogenital anomaly characterized by the triad of uterus didelphys, obstructed hemivagina, and ipsilateral renal agenesis. HWWs is usually diagnosed after menarche with symptoms of pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea, and a palpable mass due to hematocolpos or hematometra, and often associated with long-term complications such as endometriosis, pelvic adhesions, and increased risk of recurrent pregnancy loss or infertility. *Case description:* A 26-year-old woman was referred to the hospital with complaints of 8-month history of dysmenorrhea and had been diagnosed with a bicornuate uterus. Bimanual examination showed hematocolpos on the left side of the cervix and an 8 cm painless mass on both of adnexa. Speculum examination showed vaginal septae at the 7 o'clock direction, on the left side of the cervix with dark blood coming from the right side of the cervix. Her transvaginal ultrasound examination showed the presence of a bicornuate uterus. Agnesis of the right kidney and didelphys uterus with right-sided hematocolpos resulting from obstructed hemivagina were detected by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Based on clinical and radiographic examinations, the patient was diagnosed with HWWs with a huge endometrioma and treated with laparoscopic cystectomy, hysteroscopy and excision of vaginal septae. *Conclusion:* An accurate diagnosis is needed in the management of the HWWs case so that it can be treated early and can improve the patient's quality of life. Because this case is rare, health facilities need to gain an understanding of the proper diagnostic procedure.

Introduction

Herlyn-Werner-Wunderlich syndrome (HWWs) is a congenital urogenital anomaly characterized by the triad of uterus didelphys, obstructed hemivagina, and ipsilateral renal agenesis (Rusda *et al.*, 2019). The exact prevalence of HWWs is still unknown but it is reported to be 0.1% to 3.8% (Kozłowski *et al.*, 2020). It can be classified based on a completely obstructed hemivagina or incompletely obstructed hemivagina. HWWs is usually diagnosed at puberty or after menarche, with symptoms of pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea, and a palpable mass due to hematocolpos or hematometra (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2017; Khaladkar *et al.*, 2016). It is often associated with long-term complications such as endometriosis, pelvic adhesions, and an increased risk of recurrent pregnancy loss or infertility (Gupta *et al.*, 2018; Del Vescovo *et al.*, 2012). The exact etiopathogenesis of HWWs is still unknown, but Wolffian ducts play an important role in the development of internal genital organs and give rise to kidneys. They are inductor elements for the adequate fusion of the Mullerian ducts. If one of the Wolffian ducts is absent, the ipsilateral kidney and ureter will fail to fuse in the midline (Khaladkar *et al.*, 2016). Despite its rare prevalence and nonspecific symptoms, an early diagnosis needs to be established to relieve acute symptoms, preserve normal fertility, and prevent several medical complications (Del Vescovo *et al.*, 2012). The most effective modality for making a diagnosis of HWWs is Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), but ultrasonography is the modality of choice due to its wide availability (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2017). Laparoscopy can be a diagnostic and therapeutic tool in some selected cases. Menstrual suppression by oral contraceptive pills or gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogs is advised if immediate surgery can't be done (Del Vescovo *et al.*, 2012).

Method

Starting with a case search, then an examination is carried out according to the procedure. Completeness of data obtained from medical record.

Result and Discussion

Result

A 26-years-old woman was referred to the hospital with a diagnosis of a bicornuate uterus. She had previously been seen at another hospital with an 8-month history of dysmenorrhea and diagnosed with bicornuate uterus and endometrioma after it was confirmed on transvaginal ultrasound. The menarche had occurred at age 12, menses were every 26-45 days and lasted 5-10 days with moderate dysmenorrhea (VAS 4-5). She was on contraceptive pills and sexually active. The patient was in a good general condition and had normal vital signs, with a BMI of 18.3. On the abdominal examination, the uterus was palpated 2 fingers below umbilical. Bimanual examination showed hematocolpos on the left side of the cervix and an 8 cm mass on both of adnexa. Inspeculo examination showed vaginal septae at the 7 o'clock direction, on the left side of the cervix and there was dark blood coming from the right side of the cervix. The inferior pole of the mass was palpated on the digital rectal examination. Figure 1 shows the appearance of the vaginal septae.

Figure 1. Vaginal septae at the 7 o'clock direction

Transvaginal ultrasound revealed the presence of a bicornuate uterus. The endometrial line of the first uterus is 0.81 cm, and the length of another uterus was difficult to be assessed. The right ovary was on the normal size with multiple follicular cysts, and we found a 7.5 cm x 7.23 cm hypoechoic mass with internal echo on the left adnexa. Pelvic and abdominal MRI was performed and showed the presence of didelphysuterus with the right side uterus is 5.7 x 3.2 x 3 cm in size with hematometra and the left side uterus is 6.3 x 5.2 x 5.2 cm in size with hematometra also. The right hemivaginalseptae was seen on the right posterior side (7 o'clock direction) with a thickness of ± 0.5 cm which caused right hemivaginal dilatation 5.2 x 2.3 x 1.1 cm in size with blood components (volume $\pm 6,8$ cc). The right kidney is absent. These MRI findings suggested the possibility of HWWs. There was also focal adenomyosis on the left uterus and endometrioma on the left adnexa, 7.8 x 6.7 x 6,4 cm in size. Endometriosis was found on the rectovaginal space of both cervixes. Figure 2 shows the results of the MRI.

Figure 2. MRI showed the presence of didelphysuterus, right hematocolpos, endometrioma, and absence of right kidney.

Based on clinical and radiographic examinations, the patient was diagnosed with HWWs and we planned to perform laparoscopic cystectomy, hysteroscopy and excision of vaginal septae. During exploration, we found didelphys uterus: the left uterus looks enlarged due to adenomyosis ($\pm 8 \times 6 \times 6$ cm in size), the right uterus shows a normal size. At the left adnexa, we found a huge endometrioma with ± 8 cm in diameter, the right adnexa is normal.

Figure 3. Laparoscopic: didelphys uterus and endometrioma

First, we performed adhesiolysis and cystectomy. Because we had difficulty identifying the vaginal septae, we just made an incision on the right uterine fundal to reach the uterine cavity and the portio. After that, we spirt normal saline and the septae become bulge. We perform a circular incision of the vaginal septae and suture it. Figure 3 shows the image from laparoscopy. Figure 4 shows the vaginal septae before and after the incision.

Figure 4. Vaginal septae; a) before excision and b) after excision

Discussion

The cases found are rare and often have difficulty in diagnosis. HWWs is a rare syndrome that was first reported by Herlyn and Werner in 1971, whereas Wunderlich reported an association of renal aplasia with a bicornuate uterus and simple vagina in the presence of an isolated hematocervix (Zhu *et al.*, 2015). The exact etiology and pathogenesis of HWWs are still unclear, but it has been considered to represent the abnormal development of paramesonephric (Müllerian) and mesonephric (Wolffian) ducts (Khaladkar *et al.*, 2016).

HWWs is usually diagnosed at puberty or after menarche, with symptoms of pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea, and a palpable mass due to hematocolpos or hematometra (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2017; Khaladkar *et al.*, 2016). Research conducted by Jin-Hee Yu *et al.* (2022) found cases of HWWs in women aged 12 years (Yu *et al.*, 2022). This study was found in women aged 26 years. Research conducted by Sonam *et al.* (2021) in Bhutan found a 42-year-old married nulliparous woman who presented with pain on the right side of the lower abdomen and was ultimately diagnosed with HWWs (Sonam *et al.*, 2021). This shows that HWWs can be found not only at puberty and can be widespread at various ages.

In this case, there is a didelphys uterus and hemivagina. This happens through several processes. The Müllerian ducts lie lateral to the Wolffian ducts, grow downward and toward the midline, cross the Wolffian ducts, and touch each other. They fuse to form the uterovaginal canal, from which the fallopian tubes, uterus, and upper two-thirds of the vagina develop. The mesonephric duct, in addition to providing origin to the kidney, is also an inducing element for the adequate fusion of the Müllerian ducts (Orazi *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, abnormal

development of the caudal portion of one of the mesonephric ducts may be the cause of unilateral renal agenesis. On the affected side, the Müllerian duct is displaced laterally and cannot fuse with the contralateral duct, resulting in a didelphys uterus. Whereas the contralateral Müllerian duct, which cannot contact the urogenital sinus in the middle, forms a blind sac resulting in an imperforate or obstructed hemivagina (Arıkan *et al.*, 2010). It can be classified based on a completely obstructed hemivagina or incompletely obstructed hemivagina, but also can be classified into 3 types: Type I (blind hemivagina), Type II (partial reabsorption of the vaginal septum), and Type III (communicating uteri) (Khaladkar *et al.*, 2016; Zhu *et al.*, 2015).

An accurate diagnosis is needed in the management of the HWWs so that it can be treated early and can improve the patient's quality of life. The patient had previously been seen at another hospital with an 8-month history of dysmenorrhea. This is consistent with previous studies which recommended that HWWs should be suspected in patients with menstrual cramps, vaginal bleeding, dull pain in the hypogastric region, and renal agenesis (Vo Nhu *et al.*, 2021). Dysmenorrhea that appears as a common, non-specific complaint with an unusual presentation of regular menstruation may delay the diagnosis (Nishu *et al.*, 2019). Misdiagnosis is an important problem in the management of HWWs.

If this syndrome is suspected, the diagnosis can be made by ultrasound and MRI. MRI has higher sensitivity in detecting the uterine morphology and the continuity of each vagina (obstructed and non-obstructed) compared to the ultrasound. However, ultrasonography is the modality of choice because of its wide availability (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2017). Laparoscopy can be a diagnostic and therapeutic tool in some selected cases.

Delay in diagnosis can lead to complications such as endometriosis and infertility (Nishu *et al.*, 2019). This study found cases of endometrioma. Pelvic endometriosis is one of the common complications of HWWs (Miyazaki *et al.*, 2020). Endometriomas are cystic lesions that arise from the disease process of endometriosis. They are filled with dark brown endometrial fluid and are sometimes referred to as "brown cysts." The presence of an endometrioma indicates a more severe stage of endometriosis (Hoyle & Puckett, 2022). The long-term complications are endometriosis, pelvic adhesions, and an increased risk of recurrent pregnancy loss or infertility (Tzialidou-Palermo *et al.*, 2012). Obstructive anomalies are associated more with endometriosis than with nonobstructive anomalies. The incidence of primary infertility was not significantly increased in women with the didelphys uterus (Heinonen, 2000).

The choice of treatment for HWWs is hysteroscopic resection of the vaginal septum to relieve symptoms caused by the obstructed hemivagina and drainage of the hematometocolpos. In cases where septum resection cannot be accomplished or recurrent stenosis develops, unilateral hysterectomy is the treatment of choice (Ugurlucan *et al.*, 2014). Menstrual suppression by oral contraceptive pills or gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogs is advised if immediate surgery can't be done (Del Vescovo *et al.*, 2012). A multidisciplinary approach guided by gynecologists, radiologists, pediatricians, and pediatric surgeons is essential to avoid complications and achieve better outcomes (Nishu *et al.*, 2019).

Conclusion

HWWs is a rare condition with the etiopathogenesis still unknown exactly. Patient usually came in puberty with abdominal pain that cause from the obstructed hemivagina. The most effective modality for making a diagnosis of HWWs is MRI, but ultrasonography is the modality of choice due to its wide availability. Laparoscopy can be a diagnostic and therapeutic tool in some selected cases.

Recommendations

An early diagnosis needs to be established to relieve acute symptoms, preserve normal fertility, and prevent several medical complications in HWWs case. Because this case is rare, health facilities need to gain an understanding of the proper diagnostic procedure. Efforts to overcome HWWs require several stages starting from diagnosis to accurate treatment.

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